

A Comparative Study between O-RADS and IOTA Guidelines and Assessing the Efficacy of Diffusion-Weighted MRI in Differentiation of Benign and Malignant Ovarian and Adnexal Mass Lesion

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Abstract:

Objective: The purpose of this study is to assess the diagnostic performance of O-RADS ultrasound and IOTA simple rules in pre-operative discrimination of ovarian and adnexal masses as benign and malignant and to compare the accuracy of ORADS with IOTA simple rules and DW- MRI.

Methods: The study was conducted from March 1st 2023 to February 28th 2024 in the department of Radiodiagnosis at Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Silchar. The study group includes 40 patients with adnexal masses referred by gynecologists discovered during pelvic examination or by previous sonographic examination. For USG transducer having frequency of 3-12 MHz used for transvaginal sonography and curved transducer having frequency of 1-12MHz used for transabdominal sonography. MRI was performed using a Siemens 1.5 T MR system. Various conventional and advanced MR sequences DWI and ADC was used. Conventional Routine sequence was done in all cases and contrast study was done whenever indicated.

Results: In our study, we utilized two ultrasound classification systems, O-RADS and IOTA simple rules, as well as DW-MRI, to categorize benign and malignant adnexal masses. The sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of O-RADS, IOTA simple rules and DW-MRI were calculated and compared by considering histopathological diagnosis as the gold standard in adnexal masses. 40 patients with adnexal masses were evaluated. Among 40 women who participated in this study, 27 patients had benign adnexal mass lesions and 13 patients had malignant adnexal mass lesions proven by HPE. ORADS had sensitivity of 100%, specificity 88%, PPV 81% NPV 100% and accuracy 92.50%. The sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and accuracy of the IOTA simple rules were 92%, 92%, 85%, 96% and 92.50% respectively. For DW-MRI, the sensitivity was 100%, specificity 92%, PPV 86%, NPV 100% and accuracy 95%.

Conclusion: Accurately predicting the risk of malignancy in adnexal masses before surgery is crucial for optimizing patient treatment. The two well-established classification systems for distinguishing adnexal masses are O-RADS and IOTA. The IOTA simple rules are easy to use and offer high sensitivity and specificity, but they yield inconclusive results in 10% of cases. O-RADS have a higher sensitivity than IOTA simple rules in preoperative discrimination of between benign and malignant lesions, but it has a slightly lower specificity. DW-MRI with ADC values along with conventional MRI demonstrates very high sensitivity and specificity in predicting the risk of malignancy preoperatively. It can serve as a problem-solving tool for characterizing indeterminate adnexal masses.

Keywords: ORADS, IOTA, DW-MRI, Adnexal Mass Lesion.

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Introduction

Ovarian malignancy is one of the most lethal malignancies of all gynaecological cancers as it is diagnosed at later stages. It has the highest mortality rate of all gynaecologist cancers and accounts for approximately 3% of cancer among women.[1,2] Performing routine screening for high-risk individuals, increasing awareness of various risk factors, and improving diagnostic methods are essential techniques to enable early detection for

better survival rates. While evaluating with imaging, it is essential to accurately distinguish an adnexal lesion as benign or malignant for appropriate treatment. The two most used methods for making such differentiation are tumour markers and radiological imaging. Ultrasonography (USG) is the main imaging modality to scan adnexal masses of uncertain origin and contributes significantly to the diagnosis of pathologies of the pelvis and abdomen.

Several classification systems have been devised to distinguish benign and malignant adnexal masses, by combining USG findings with other modalities to overcome these limitations. One such major effort at standardization is done by the International Ovarian Tumour Analysis (IOTA). The IOTA Simple Rules classify adnexal masses into benign, malignant and inconclusive with respect to the specific ultrasound findings. This uniform method is designed to enhance diagnostic accuracy and assist in management. [3] The American College of Radiology (ACR) developed the Ovarian-Adnexal Reporting and Data System (O-RADS) to standardize ultrasound risk stratification and also proposed management recommendations for ovarian and other adnexal masses.[4] For indeterminate adnexal lesions Computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are usually performed for further assessment. They can determine the extension of the disease into the abdomen, and the presence of nodal spread and help to determine the origin (gastrointestinal system, urinary tract and retroperitoneum) or nature (benign vs. malignant) of the mass when ultrasound findings are equivocal or additional details are needed for treatment planning.[5]

DWI-MRI plays an important role in preoperative discrimination. The ADC values calculated from DWI-MRI enable distinguishing benign from malignant masses. The application of this modality significantly raises diagnosis confidence through functional imaging and thus guides surgical management without the exposure to ionizing radiation associated with CTs.

Methods and Materials

The study was conducted from march 1st 2023 to February 29th 2024 in the department of Radiodiagnosis at Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Silchar. The study group includes 40 patients with adnexal masses referred by gynecologists discovered during pelvic examination or by previous sonographic examination. Written consent was obtained from all the participants before the study.

Technique

For USG transducer having frequency of 3-12 MHz used for transvaginal sonography and curved transducer having frequency of 1-12MHz used for transabdominal sonography. MRI evaluation was carried out using SIEMENS AVANTO FIT 1.5T SCANNER. Various conventional and advanced

MR pulse sequences were used. Images with multiple b-values, between 0,400,800 s/mm², were acquired. On MRI, we evaluated the signal strength intensity on DW images. The signal intensity was recorded for each lesion on the DW images, even when the highest intensity was localized. Lesions were classified as abnormal if the signal strength intensity on DW images was strong or very strong. Lesions exhibiting abnormal signal intensity were considered malignant ovarian lesions. The location of abnormal signal intensity in the lesions on DWI was assessed by referring to the axial and sagittal T1 and T2 MR images.

ADC values were estimated using the workstation's standard software (Diffusion Calculation) with a circular operator-defined ROI measuring 3 mm on the solid components of the lesion. For large lesions, the mean value was calculated from three measurements taken in three different ROIs on the same slice. Necrotic areas were excluded from the measurements in solid lesions. For lesions exhibiting wide variations in ADC values, both the highest and lowest values were recorded

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients with suspicion of adnexal masses on pelvic examination or adnexal mass identified during sonographic examination.
- Conservatively managed patients with adnexal masses with adequate follow up information.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Pregnant patients.
- Patient with insufficient follow-up information.
- Premenopausal women with physiological category of ovarian lesions like follicle and corpus luteum (O RADS- 1 lesion).

Data entered in MS excel sheet and SPSS version 26.0 was used for statistical analysis. Qualitative variables were summarized using frequencies and percentages. Association among the study groups is assessed with the help of a chi-square test. 'p-value less than 0.05 is taken as statistically significant.

Results

Most of the patients with adnexal masses in our study fall within the age group of 31-40 yrs.

The youngest patient in our study was 28 years old and the eldest was 68 years old female, the mean age (SD) was 43.95 years. Premenopausal group consists of 24 patients (60%), and postmenopausal group consists of 16 patients (40.0%).

Table 1: Frequency of adnexal masses in different age groups

Age Distribution		
	Frequency	Percent
Upto 30yrs	1	2.5
31-40yrs	21	52.5
41-50yrs	5	12.5

51-60yrs	8	20
61-70 yrs	5	12.5
Total	40	100
Mean +/-=43.95		

Age distribution of adnexal masses

Figure 1: Age distribution of adnexal masses

Table 2: Frequency of adnexal masses according to the Menopausal Status of the patient

Menopausal Status		
	Frequency	Percent
Premenopausal	24	60
Postmenopausal	16	40
Total	40	100

Figure 2: Menopausal Status

In our study, Premenopausal group consists of 24 patients (60%), and postmenopausal group consists of 16 patients (40%).

Table 3: comparison of benign and malignant lesions in different age group

		HPE Diagnosis			Total	X ² - value	P-value (pearson's chi square test)
		Malig-nant	Benign				
Age	UPTO 30YRS	Count	1	0	1	25.983	0.0005**
		%	7.70%	0.00%	2.5%		
	31-40YRS	Count	0	21	21		
		%	0.00%	77.80%	52.50%		
	41-50YRS	Count	2	3	5		
		%	15.40%	11.10%	12.50%		
	51-60YRS	Count	5	3	8		
		%	38.50%	11.10%	20.0%		
	61-70YRS	Count	5	0	5		
		%	38.50%	0.0%	12.50%		
Total	Count	13	27	40			
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%			

****Highly statistical significance at p <0.01 level**

Figure 3: comparison of distribution of benign and malignant lesions in different age group

Malignant lesions were common in the 51-60 yrs age group compared to benign lesions which were common in 31-40 yrs age group. The above table shows comparison of malignant and benign lesions in different age groups with p value <0.01 which shows high statistical significance.

Table 4: Comparison of malignancy rate between unilocular and multilocular cystic Adnexal lesions

		HPE Diagnosis			Total	X ² - value	P -value (Pearson chi square test)
		Malignant	Benign				
Locularity	Unilocular	Count	1	19	20	13.805	0.0005
		%	8.30%	73.10%	52.60%		
	Multilocular	Count	11	7	18		
		%	91.70%	26.90%	47.40%		
Total	Count	12	26	38			
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%			

**** Highly statistical significance at p <0.01**

Figure 4: Locularity and malignancy rate

On comparing malignancy rate between unilocular and multilocular tumor with HPE, it is observed that larger proportion (91.7%) of malignant lesions were found in Multilocular adnexal lesions than the unilocular (8.30%) lesions, with a significant p value.

Table 5: Comparison of malignancy rate with the presence of solid component within the adnexal lesions

			HPE Diagnosis		Total	X ² -value	P value (Pearson chi square test)
			Malignant	Benign			
Solid component	Absent	Count	2	26	28	29.405	0.0005**
		%	16.70%	100.0%	73.70%		
	Present	Count	10	0	10		
		%	83.30%	0.0%	26.30%		
Total	Count	12	26	38			
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%			

** Highly statistical significance at p <0.01 level

Figure 5: Solid component between HPE diagnosis

Larger proportion of malignant lesions was found in adnexal lesions with solid components (83.30%) than lesions without solid components. (16.70 %). Malignancy was more common in the cystic adnexal lesions with solid components than lesions without solid components which were found to be statistically significant.

Table 6: Comparison of presence of Papillary Projection within the adnexal lesion and malignancy rate

			HPE Diagnosis		Total	X ² -value	P-value (Pearson chi square test)
			Malignant	Benign			
Papillary projection	No projection	Count	5	27	32	16.927	0.0005**
		%	45.45%	100.0%	84.21%		
	1-3 projection	Count	3	0	3		
		%	27.30%	0.0%	8.10%		

	>=4projec-tion	Count	3	0	3		
		%	27.30%	0.0%	8.10%		
Total		Count	11	27	38		
		%	1000.0%	100.0%	100.0%		

** Highly statistical significance at p <0.01 level

Figure 6: Comparison of presence of Papillary Projection within the adnexal lesion and malignancy rate

Malignant lesions were found more in adnexal lesions with papillary projections (54.6%), than lesions without papillary projections (45.45%). Thus, malignancy was more common in the cystic adnexal lesion with papillary projections, than lesions without papillary projections which were found to be statistically significant (P < 0.01). Presence of 1-3 and more than four papillary projections are highly suggestive of malignancy.

Table 7: Comparison of Colour Doppler Score with Malignancy Rate

Colour doppler Score	HPE Diagnosis				Total	X ² value	P value (Pearson chi square test)
		Count	Malignant	Benign			
No flow	Count	0	24	24	30.623	0.0005**	
	%	0.0%	88.90	60.0%			
Minimal	Count	3	2	5			
	%	23.10%	7.40%	12.50%			
Moderate	Count	6	1	7			
	%	46.20%	3.70%	17.50%			
Very strong	Count	4	0	4			
	%	38.80%	0.0%	10.0%			
Total	Count	13	27	40			
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%			

** Highly statistical significance at p <0.01 level

Figure 7: Comparison of Colour Doppler Score with Malignancy Rate

Malignancy was more common in the cystic adnexal lesions with moderate and strong blood flow, than lesions with minimal or no flow which were found to be statistically significant.

Table 8: Comparison of ORADS, IOTA simple rules, Diffusion parameter of the adnexal lesion

		HPE Diagnosis				
		Malignant	Benign	Total		
ORADS	Malignant	13	3	16	Sensitivity	100.0
	benign	0	24	24	Specificity	88%
Total		13	27	40	PPV	81%
		HPE Diagnosis			Total	
		Malignant	Benign		Sensitivity	100%
IOTA	Malignant	12	2	14	Specificity	92%
	Benign	1	25	26	PPV	85%
Total		13	27	40	NPV	96%
		HPE Diagnosis			Total	
		Malignant	Benign		Sensitivity	100%
DWI	Malignant	13	2	15	Specificity	92%
	Benign	0	25	25	PPV	86%
Total		13	27	40	NPV	100%
		HPE Diagnosis			Total	
		Malignant	Benign		Sensitivity	100%
		Malignant	Benign		Specificity	92%
		Malignant	Benign		PPV	86%
		Malignant	Benign		NPV	100%
Total		13	27	40	Accuracy	94%

Figure 8: Accuracy of ORADS

On comparing ORADS with HPE, the sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of O-RADS for the diagnosis of malignant adnexal masses were 100%, 88%, 81% and 100% respectively with p- value <0.01 which is of high statistical significance.

Figure 9: Accuracy of IOTA simple rules

On comparing IOTA with HPE Diagnosis, the sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of IOTA simple rules for the diagnosis of malignant adnexal masses were 92%, 92%, 85% and 96% respectively with p- value= <0.01 which is of high statistical significance.

Figure 10: Accuracy of Diffusion weighted images

On comparing Diffusion Restriction with HPE Diagnosis, the Sensitivity is 100.0%, Specificity 92%, PPV 86.0%, NPV 100.0% and accuracy is 95.0%, with p- value= <0.01 which is of high statistical significance.

Table 9: Comparison of ADC Value with HPE

ADC Value Comparison with HPE				
		HPE Diagnosis		Total
		Malignant	Benign	
ADC Value	<1.05	12	1	13
	≥ 1.05	1	26	27
	Total	13	27	40

Figure 11: Accuracy of ADC

The above Figure-11 shows the comparison of ADC Values with HPE Diagnosis, with a p- value= 0.0005 <0.01 , which is of high statistical significance with a Sensitivity of 92%, Specificity 96%, PPV 92 %, NPV 96% and accuracy 95%.

Discussion

The two significant and effective ultrasound classification systems for adnexal masses (O-RADS and IOTA simple rules), along with DW-MRI, offer a structured approach to managing patients with these masses. They aid in identifying malignant adnexal masses and determining appropriate treatment options. While numerous studies have validated the malignancy risk stratification of

adnexal masses using IOTA and DW-MRI, however limited studies are there on prospective and external validation research of ORADS.

In this study, we utilized two ultrasound classification systems, O-RADS and IOTA simple rules, as well as DW-MRI, to categorize benign and malignant adnexal masses. The goal was to assess the malignancy rates, validity and reliability of O-RADS in patients with adnexal masses. For contextual comparison, we also conducted a parallel analysis using the established IOTA simple rules and DW-MRI recommendations. Thus, this study aimed to compare O-RADS with IOTA simple rules and DW-MRI. The sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of O-RADS, IOTA simple rules and DW-MRI were calculated and compared by considering histopathological diagnosis as the gold standard in adnexal masses.

The age range in our study was 20-70 years, with a mean age of 43 years. Most of the ovarian tumours were found in the age group of 31-40 years followed by 41-50 years, and 61-70 years. Most benign ovarian tumours were found in the age group of 31-40 years whereas malignant tumours were found after 40 years. An almost similar finding was also reported by M J Merino et al(1993)[6], Mani Krishna et al(2015)[7], Modepalli et al (2016)[8] in their respective studies. M J Merino et al (1993) found that the incidence of benign epithelial tumours peaks between the ages of 20 years and 40 years and older women had the most aggressive forms of ovarian cancer which is comparable with our study.

The mean age of diagnosis in our study was 43.5 years. Similar results were found by Modepalli et al (2016), the mean age of diagnosis in their study was 42.4 years and age varied from 14-76 years.

In our study 56% of tumours were benign and 30% were malignant comparable with the study conducted by Gupta (2019) et al and Ranjoalkar P et al (2020). In our study, forty adnexal masses are pathologically diagnosed. Among forty women who participated in this study, 27 patients had benign adnexal mass lesions and 13 patients had malignant adnexal mass lesions proven by HPE. 24 patients (60%) were premenopausal, and 16 patients (40%) were postmenopausal. It is observed that malignant adnexal masses were more common in postmenopausal women (92.30%). In our study amongst all benign lesions, serous cystadenoma (15%) is the most common benign lesions whereas amongst all malignant lesion's serous cystadenocarcinoma (10%) is the most common in our study. Considering combined O-RADS -4 and O-RADS- 5 as indicators of malignancy, O-RADS classified 24 adnexal masses (60%) as benign and 16 adnexal masses (40%) as malignant.

The sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and accuracy of O-RADS for diagnosing malignant adnexal masses were 100%, 88%, 81%, 100% and 92.50% respectively.

The findings of our study is comparable with the studies done by Mohammad Abd Alkhalik Basha et al.[9] Yuyango Guo et al.[10], and Lano Cao et al.[11].

Table 10: Diagnostic Accuracy of ORADS

Study	Sensitivity	Specificity
Mohammad Abd Alkhalik Basha et al(2018)[9]	97%	93%
Lan Cao et al (2021)[11]	98.7%	83.2%
Yuyang Guo et al(2022)[10]	91%	81.9%
AK Heitt et al. (2021)[12]	100%	46.4%
Present Study	100%	88%

When using only M features, no M and B features or both M and B features as malignancy predictors, the IOTA simple rules categorized 26 adnexal masses (65%) as benign and 14 adnexal masses (35%) as malignant. The sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and accuracy of the IOTA simple rules for

diagnosing malignant adnexal masses were 92%, 92%, 85%, 96% and 92.50% respectively. The findings of our study is comparable with the studies done by Mohammad Abd Alkhalik Basha et al [9], Yuyango Guo et al[10] and Lano Cao et al.[11]

Table 11: Diagnostic Accuracy of IOTA

Study	Sensitivity	Specificity
Mohammad Abd Alkhalik Basha et al(2018)[9]	92.1%	93.2%
Yuyang Guo et al(2022)[10]	81.4%	92.4%
AK Heitt et al. (2021)[12]	100%	51.8%
Present Study	92%	92%

For DW-MRI, the sensitivity was 100%, specificity 92%, PPV 86%, NPV 100% and accuracy 95%. The differences in ADC values for the solid components

of benign and malignant tumours to distinguish between them were determined.

The mean ADC value for benign lesions was $1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, while for malignant lesions it was $0.80 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, with a cut-off point of $1.05 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and a p-value < 0.05 , indicating statistical significance with a sensitivity of 92% and specificity of 96%. Our findings are similar to the study done by Li and colleagues et al. (2012)[13] where they assessed the ADC values of benign and malignant ovarian surface epithelial tumours prior to surgery. In their study, the mean ADC value for benign tumours was $1.69 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, (95% CI: $1.58\text{--}1.80 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$), while in the case of malignant tumours, it was $1.03 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.22 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. It was seen that a cut-off ADC of $1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ was associated with sensitivity and specificity rates of 90.1% and 89.9%, respectively by ROC analysis.

Our study also comparable with the findings of Xinhua Fan et al (2015)[14] study. In their research, the accuracy, sensitivity and specificity of DW-MRI in distinguishing malignancies from benign ovarian tumours were 89.77%, 93.10% and 83.33% respectively.

Our study is also comparable with the study by Rahma Farghaly Ali et al.[15], who performed a prospective study that included 51 patients with complex cystic or solid adnexal lesions detected on the gynaecological ultrasonographic examination and also conventional MRI followed by DWI. Their mean ADC values for malignant ovarian tumours were 0.977 ± 0.32 , while the ADC values for the benign ovarian lesions were 1.516 ± 0.6 . Their study showed 100% sensitivity, 71.4% specificity, 100% PPV and 74.2% NPV.

When considering both O-RADS 4 and O-RADS 5 as an indicator of malignant lesions, O-RADS

presented significantly better performance compared to IOTA simple rules (p value < 0.05) with a statistically higher sensitivity for malignancy but almost equal to DW-MRI (p value < 0.05). However, the specificity of DW-MRI and the IOTA simple rules was higher compared to O-RADS (p < 0.05). For the three classification systems, the positive predictive value and negative predictive value were both fairly high; $>70\%$ and $>90\%$ respectively. The far better sensitivity of O-RADS than IOTA simple rules may be attributed to the more detailed description and interpretation in O-RADS to determine in which adnexal mass (AM) there is no need for follow-up, conservative follow-up, or the necessity for surgical removal.

In contrast, the IOTA simple rules did not give sufficient guidance for management. Notably, in our study, the O-RADS exhibited a higher sensitivity of 100% with a slightly lower specificity of 88% in diagnosing adnexal mass lesions compared to DW-MRI and IOTA, while it maintained specificity of above 80%. That is, more malignant lesions were correctly classified as malignant with O-RADS, leading to an increase in true-positive results and a reduction in false-negative results.

However, as ORADS has lower specificity and thereby an increase in the false positives: more benign adnexal masses would be diagnosed as malignant and would, therefore, lead to the respective overtreatment by unnecessary surgical procedures. For false positives, no survival is affected, but due to the low specificity within O-RADS, there may arise many cases of over treating adnexal masses. This must be taken into account in further releases of O-RADS.

Case 1: Serous Cystadenocarcinoma

Figure 12: A) Transabdominal ultrasound reveals a multiloculated cystic lesion with irregular inner margin, with internal papillary projection. Colour Doppler ultrasound reveals moderate flow (CS-3).

Categorized as ORADS-5, IOTA-M. B) Axial T2FS image shows multilocular cystic lesion with internal papillary projections C) Axial contrast-enhanced MR image of lesion shows enhancement of solid papillary projections

Figure 13: D) and F) Axial DWI and ADC map demonstrate diffusion restriction within the papillary projection of the lesion with ADC value $=.0.86 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$
 Case 2: Mucinous Cystadenoma

Figure 14: A) Transabdominal USG shows a Multilocular cystic lesion of size 11.5cm with smooth internal septations and low level internal echoes showing no vascularity on colour doppler study, CS=1, consistent with (ORADS-4), (IOTA-B5) B) Axial T1WI image showing multilocular cystic lesion with smooth internal septations with variable intensity in different locules features consistent with Mucinous Cystadenoma

Case 3: Mucinous cystadenocarcinoma

Figure 15: A) Grayscale Transabdominal USG B) Colour doppler study shows Multilocular cystic lesion sized 13cm with internal solid component with diffuse low-level internal echogenicity showing internal vascularity on colour doppler study, CS=4 consistent with ORADS-5 & Malignant IOTA lesion

Figure 16: C) Axial T1WI and D) Axial T2WI MRI image showing Multilocular cystic lesion with internal solid components with variable intensity in different locules

Figure 17: E) Axial T1+C image showing enhancement of solid components

Figure 18: F) Axial DWI and G) Axial ADC image shows diffusion restriction of solid components

Case 4: Metastases

Figure 18: A) Transabdominal USG shows complex mass in the bilateral adnexa predominantly solid in nature showing moderate internal vascularity on colour doppler flow (CS=3) consistent with ORADS-5 lesion and Malignant IOTA. B) Axial T2FS image shows both ovaries are replaced by heterointense complex mass lesions predominantly solid in nature

Figure 19: C) Axial DWI and D) Axial ADC image show restricted diffusion of the solid component with ADC value $0.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$

Case 5: Fibroma

Figure 20: A) Transabdominal Grayscale USG and B) Colour Doppler study shows a well-defined 5cm sized hypochoic solid lesion showing no vascularity CS=1 consistent with ORADS-3 lesion & benign IOTA

Figure 21: C) Sagittal T1WI and D) axial T2WI images shows a well-defined solid hypointense lesion showing no enhancement on post contrast study Consistent with fibroma

Figure 22: E) and F) Axial DWI/ADC images shows diffusion restriction with ADC value $1.06 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$

Conclusion

Accurately predicting the risk of malignancy in adnexal masses before surgery is crucial for

optimizing patient treatment. The two well-established classification systems for distinguishing adnexal masses are O-RADS and IOTA.

The IOTA simple rules are easy to use and offer high sensitivity and specificity, but they yield inconclusive results in 10% of cases.

O-RADS has a higher sensitivity than IOTA simple rules in preoperative discrimination between benign and malignant lesions, but it has a slightly lower specificity, leading to the misdiagnosis of some benign adnexal masses as malignant and resulting in overtreatment.

DW-MRI along with conventional MRI demonstrates very high sensitivity and specificity in predicting the risk of malignancy preoperatively. It can serve as a problem-solving tool for characterizing indeterminate adnexal masses. The development of diffusion analysis, which uses ADC values and visual assessment of DW signals to characterize sonographically indeterminate adnexal masses, helps radiologists improve lesion characterization, particularly for benign lesions, and assists clinicians in avoiding unnecessary surgeries.

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